

Deep learning for autonomous distributed aperture control in the Small ExoLife Finder (SELF) telescope

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ABSTRACT

The ExoLife Finder (ELF), a 35–50-meter-class Fizeau interferometric telescope, was conceived for the detection of potential biosignatures on exoplanets through direct imaging. Prior to its full-scale implementation, the Small ExoLife Finder (SELF), a 3.5-meter prototype, serves as a testbed for advanced technologies currently under development at the Laboratory for Innovation in Opto-Mechanics (LIOM) at the Instituto de Astrofísica de Canarias.

One of the main innovations in SELF is the integration of machine learning to achieve the real-time, high-cadence performance required to control its complex optomechanical system and cophase its 15 sub-apertures. Precise cophasing is crucial, particularly under dynamic conditions such as atmospheric turbulence, where the optical path difference between segments must be controlled to a small fraction of the wavelength. A convolutional neural network (CNN) architecture has been implemented, within a supervised regression framework, designed to learn the nonlinear mappings between the degrees of freedom of each sub-aperture. Using focal-plane wavefront sensing data, the CNN provide the necessary adjustments to maintain diffraction-limited performance, an essential condition for high-contrast imaging.

This approach has been validated using synthetic datasets generated from both an instrumental simulation implemented in HCIPy and a detailed optical model of the telescope developed in Ansys Zemax OpticStudio. Preliminary results demonstrate the potential of the developed approach in both scenarios. Overall, the CNN-based control strategy highlights the feasibility of autonomous, data-driven control systems for future large-scale interferometric telescopes.

Keywords: Machine Learning, Distributed Aperture Control, Fizeau Interferometry, Wavefront Sensing, High-Contrast Imaging, Small ExoLife Finder (SELF), Exoplanet Imaging

1. INTRODUCTION

The ExoLife Finder (ELF) is a planned 35–50-meter-class hybrid telescope specifically designed to search for biosignatures on exoplanets through direct imaging [1]. The feasibility of ELF relies on several technological innovations currently under development at the Laboratory for Innovation in Opto-Mechanics (LIOM) at the Instituto de Astrofísica de Canarias. These innovations are being validated using a 3.5-meter prototype, hereafter referred to as the Small ExoLife Finder (SELF) [1, 2].

SELF features a hybrid architecture that combines conventional imaging with Fizeau interferometry. Its distributed aperture consists of 15 primary and 15 secondary mirrors arranged in a one-to-one configuration. To produce a high-resolution image at the focal plane, the beams from each primary–secondary pair must be coherently combined. In particular, the optical path difference between aperture pairs must be controlled to a small fraction of the operating wavelength.

The distributed design of SELF introduces an inherent cophasing challenge. This problem is being addressed using focal-plane wavefront sensing [1, 2], optionally complemented by photonic devices, and machine learning (ML) approaches [3, 4, 5].

However, during the design and validation stages, it is essential to determine the degrees of freedom (DOF) required for each primary–secondary pair to achieve a nominally cophased configuration. Specifically, a reference alignment must first be established, which can subsequently be refined or actively controlled using focal-plane images and/or photonic devices. Furthermore, understanding the coupling between perturbations is critical, as is the ability to identify the corresponding compensatory adjustments whenever possible.

ML was employed to develop a regression model, within a supervised learning framework, trained on synthetic data generated from a telescope model implemented in HCIPy [6]. HCIPy employs Fourier optics to propagate the electric field from the telescope pupil to the focal plane, enabling efficient simulations that incorporate atmospheric turbulence and instrumental aberrations.

To further assess the robustness of the proposed approach, the regression model was also evaluated using an independent, high-fidelity optical simulation of the telescope developed in Ansys Zemax OpticStudio [7]. In contrast to the Fourier-optics framework used in HCIPy, Zemax performs numerical ray tracing in which rays propagate and interact with optical surfaces to form the final image. This is, an explicit geometric description of the optical system is defined, including custom geometric specifications, material properties, and mechanical DOF. This enables analysis of how optical parameters and mechanical tolerances affect the image quality at the focal plane, providing a realistic representation of the telescope optical design. To reduce the complexity of the full system while preserving its essential behavior, a simplified configuration consisting of four primary–secondary pairs was considered, with variations restricted to the DOF of the primary mirrors.

In this work, we investigated the capability of ML approaches, particularly a convolutional neural network (CNN), to learn the nonlinear mapping between the primary sub-aperture misalignments and their corresponding focal-plane signatures. Therefore, the system DOF can be identified and controlled using focal-plane information alone. The results demonstrate the potential of data-driven methods to address high-dimensional cophasing problems in distributed-aperture telescopes. Specifically, this framework enables the validation and optimization of alignment strategies within SELF, both in simplified simulations and in more detailed optical models, facilitating the critical transition from incoherence to full coherence in the system.

2. METHODS

2.1 HCIPy Telescope Model and Datasets

A simplified configuration of SELF, considering only four primary mirrors, was implemented in HCIPy [6], an open-source Python package designed to simulate high-contrast imaging systems using Fourier-based wave-optics propagation. This approach enables physically consistent modeling of diffraction effects and atmospheric turbulence. At this stage, atmospheric phase screens were not included, as the initial objective was to isolate the effect of each aperture’s DOF on the point spread function (PSF) and to identify the main differences between the two modeling approaches.

The primary mirrors had a diameter of 0.5 m and were arranged on a circular array with a diameter of 3.5 m, following the SELF design [1, 2]. The mirrors were positioned at azimuthal angles of 0° , 72° , 192° , and 264° relative to the array center, corresponding to pairs 1 through 4. The effective focal length of the system was 32.5 m, and the pupil grid was sampled with 512×512 pixels.

The telescope model was used to compute the focal-plane response of the system, i.e., the PSF, under controlled perturbations of the primary mirrors’ DOF. In this proof of concept, piston and tilts about the X and Y axes

were considered. Each primary aperture was sequentially selected, and random perturbations were applied to each of its DOF before computing the resulting focal-plane image. The perturbation range for piston was $\pm 10 \mu\text{m}$, while the tilt range was $\pm 4 \mu\text{rad}$.

Simulations were performed for both monochromatic illumination at a wavelength of $1 \mu\text{m}$ and broadband illumination centered at $1 \mu\text{m}$ with a bandwidth of 100 nm . Two datasets were generated based on these illumination conditions, each consisting of 10000 samples.

2.2 Zemax Telescope Model and Datasets

A high-fidelity optical model of the simplified four primary-secondary pair configuration was implemented in Ansys Zemax OpticStudio [7]. The simulation combines ray-tracing and wave-optics propagation to compute the focal-plane response of the system, in particular the Huygens PSF, under controlled perturbations of the primary mirrors' DOF.

In order to compute the Huygens PSF, a grid of rays is launched through the optical system, where each ray represents a wavelet with a specific amplitude and phase. The diffraction intensity at any point on the image plane is obtained as the squared magnitude of the coherent sum of these wavelets. This process is repeated over the image grid to construct the full PSF.

In contrast to the HCIPy simulations, where a single effective focal length is used for the entire system, in Zemax each primary and secondary mirror is modeled with its actual focal length. The mirrors' diameters and positions were matched to the HCIPy configuration, and only piston and tilts about the X and Y axes were considered. Furthermore, in Zemax, piston and tilts are defined in a local coordinate system centered on each primary mirror, with the z-axis aligned with the mirror surface normal, whereas in HCIPy these perturbations are applied directly on the apertures.

Figure 1 shows the implemented model, illustrating the configuration of the four primary-secondary pairs and the corresponding optical path used for focal-plane image generation.

Figure 1. 3D layout of the telescope model implemented in Ansys Zemax OpticStudio [7], showing the configuration of the four primary-secondary pairs and the optical path used for focal-plane image generation. The inset provides a magnified view of the corresponding secondary mirrors.

Zemax can be accessed through its Python API, enabling automated dataset generation. Similarly to the process carried out in HCIPy, a custom Python script was developed to interface with the optical model, select a primary mirror, apply random perturbations to its DOF (piston and tilts about the X and Y axes), and compute the resulting focal-plane image using the Huygens PSF.

Several datasets were generated to progressively increase the dimensionality of the problem. Initially, two datasets were created using the on-axis field, each designed to isolate the effect of a single degree of freedom in one sub-aperture. In the first dataset, the tilt of the primary mirror (pair 1) was varied along the X axis to generate 1000 images over a range of $\pm 10 \mu\text{rad}$. In the second dataset, the tilt of the same mirror was varied along the Y axis, producing an additional 1000 images across the same range. These two datasets were referred to as independently varied.

Subsequently, piston was introduced, and all three DOF were applied simultaneously to the same primary mirror (pair 1), generating a new dataset comprising 1000 samples. This dataset was referred to as the simultaneously varied dataset. Finally, two primary mirrors (pairs 1 and 2) were simultaneously perturbed to generate a dataset consisting of approximately 1400 samples. Overall, piston was sampled within $\pm 50 \mu\text{m}$, while tilts were sampled within $\pm 10 \mu\text{rad}$. The operating wavelength was set to $1 \mu\text{m}$.

2.3 CNN-Based Regression Framework

The ML approach was formulated as a regression problem to estimate the magnitude of the perturbations applied to each primary aperture. The model takes as input the focal-plane intensity distribution, represented by the PSFs. The outputs, which serve as labels in the supervised learning framework, correspond to the ground-truth piston and tilt corrections, namely tilts about the X and Y axes, required to restore the system to its nominal alignment.

The implemented regression model employed a straightforward architecture designed to extract relevant features from the focal-plane images within the generated datasets. The neural network architecture consisted of four 2D convolutional layers with instance normalization, rectified linear unit (ReLU) activations, max pooling, and 25% dropout, followed by two fully connected layers. The first fully connected layer included layer normalization, a ReLU activation, and 25% dropout, whereas the second layer was used to predict the output values required to correct the system alignment.

Note that, under any illumination scenario, the global piston of the telescope cannot be determined from focal-plane images. For the HCIPy datasets with monochromatic illumination, this limitation is further enhanced by phase wrapping, which introduces a degeneracy in the measured piston differences. Therefore, only eight parameters were predicted in this case, corresponding to the tilts along the X and Y axes for each primary mirror. In contrast, for broadband illumination, part of this degeneracy is lifted, allowing the estimation of 14 parameters: eight tilt parameters and six piston-difference parameters between mirrors in pairs.

For the Zemax dataset, two outputs were predicted for the independently varied datasets, corresponding to tilts along the X and Y axes for the pair 1. For the simultaneously varied dataset, three outputs were predicted, as piston was also included. Finally, for the dataset in which two primary mirrors (pairs 1 and 2) were perturbed, four parameters were predicted, corresponding to the tilts along the X and Y axes for these mirrors.

All datasets were split into training and test sets (80/20%). The training sets were further divided into training and validation subsets (80/20%) using 10-fold cross-validation. Mean Squared Error (MSE) was used as the loss function, and the CNN was optimized using the Adam optimizer [8] with a learning rate of 0.001 and a batch size of 16. Early stopping with a patience of 10 epochs was employed to prevent overfitting, together with model checkpointing to save the weights whenever the validation loss improved, ensuring recovery of the best-performing model for each fold. The resulting models were then evaluated on the test datasets.

Metrics from the 10 folds were aggregated to obtain the mean and standard deviation for each error measure: root mean square error (RMSE), mean absolute error (MAE), and the coefficient of determination (R^2) between the predicted and true values.

Training and inference were performed on the IACTEC computational system, equipped with an Intel® Core™ Ultra 9 185H CPU (2.5 GHz), 32 GB of system RAM, and an NVIDIA GeForce RTX 4070 GPU with 8 GB of dedicated memory. For the HCIPy datasets, the regression model was trained in approximately four hours for monochromatic illumination and roughly 10 hours for the broadband case. For the Zemax datasets, which were considerably smaller, models were trained in less than 8 minutes for all datasets.

3. RESULTS

3.1 HCIPy Telescope Model

The model performance for tilts along the X and Y axes, evaluated using RMSE, MAE and R^2 , is summarized in Tables 1 and 2 for monochromatic and broadband illumination, respectively. Performance for piston reconstruction under broadband illumination is reported in Table 3. For illustrative purposes, scatter plots of the predicted versus true tilt values are shown in Figure 2 for both illumination conditions. Figure 3 displays the corresponding plots for piston differences under broadband illumination.

Under monochromatic illumination, tilt reconstruction achieved an RMSE of approximately $0.17 \mu\text{rad}$ over a $\pm 4 \mu\text{rad}$ dynamic range, corresponding to about 4% of the maximum tilt amplitude. Reconstruction accuracy for Y-axis tilts was uniform across mirror pairs, indicating spatially consistent performance. However, for X-axis tilts, statistically significant differences were detected among sub-apertures (Friedman test, $p \leq 0.01$). Post-hoc

Table 1. Performance of the trained model for monochromatic illumination in estimating tilts along the X and Y axes. Metrics reported include the root mean square error (RMSE), mean absolute error (MAE), and the coefficient of determination (R^2) between predicted and ground-truth (true) values. The reported values correspond to the mean and standard deviation obtained from 10-fold cross-validation during model training.

DOF	Pair	RMSE (μrad)	MAE (μrad)	R^2
Tilt Y	1	0.1749 ± 0.0199	0.1379 ± 0.0156	0.9942 ± 0.0014
	2	0.1710 ± 0.0150	0.1341 ± 0.0125	0.9944 ± 0.0010
	3	0.1650 ± 0.0125	0.1313 ± 0.0100	0.9949 ± 0.0008
	4	0.1679 ± 0.0101	0.1328 ± 0.0083	0.9947 ± 0.0006
Tilt X	1	0.1695 ± 0.0210	0.1338 ± 0.0174	0.9944 ± 0.0015
	2	0.1789 ± 0.0169	0.1415 ± 0.0134	0.9940 ± 0.0012
	3	0.1567 ± 0.0134	0.1236 ± 0.0112	0.9952 ± 0.0008
	4	0.1770 ± 0.0183	0.1403 ± 0.0149	0.9940 ± 0.0012

Table 2. Performance of the trained model for broadband illumination in estimating tilts along the X and Y axes. Metrics reported include the root mean square error (RMSE), mean absolute error (MAE), and the coefficient of determination (R^2) between predicted and ground-truth (true) values. The reported values correspond to the mean and standard deviation obtained from 10-fold cross-validation during model training.

DOF	Pair	RMSE (μrad)	MAE (μrad)	R^2
Tilt Y	1	0.5315 ± 0.0580	0.3757 ± 0.0377	0.9450 ± 0.0119
	2	0.5682 ± 0.0448	0.4056 ± 0.0369	0.9374 ± 0.0098
	3	0.4670 ± 0.0395	0.3319 ± 0.0275	0.9588 ± 0.0070
	4	0.4850 ± 0.0448	0.3436 ± 0.0299	0.9562 ± 0.0081
Tilt X	1	0.5424 ± 0.0539	0.3731 ± 0.0367	0.9440 ± 0.0110
	2	0.5869 ± 0.0432	0.4128 ± 0.0318	0.9373 ± 0.0094
	3	0.4553 ± 0.0438	0.3267 ± 0.0314	0.9621 ± 0.0076
	4	0.5053 ± 0.0456	0.3445 ± 0.0331	0.9510 ± 0.0089

Table 3. Performance of the trained model for broadband illumination in estimating piston differences between mirrors. Metrics reported include the root mean square error (RMSE), mean absolute error (MAE), and the coefficient of determination (R^2) between predicted and ground-truth (true) values. The reported values correspond to the mean and standard deviation obtained from 10-fold cross-validation during model training.

DOF	Pair	RMSE (μm)	MAE (μm)	R^2
Piston difference	1-2	1.5877 ± 0.1065	1.0632 ± 0.0717	0.9605 ± 0.0052
	1-3	1.1589 ± 0.0805	0.7543 ± 0.0597	0.9791 ± 0.0030
	1-4	1.5784 ± 0.0816	1.0592 ± 0.0686	0.9613 ± 0.0039
	2-3	1.4864 ± 0.0978	0.9829 ± 0.0562	0.9667 ± 0.0044
	2-4	1.1974 ± 0.0862	0.7835 ± 0.0512	0.9780 ± 0.0032
	3-4	1.5981 ± 0.0935	1.0622 ± 0.0544	0.9618 ± 0.0045

pairwise Wilcoxon tests with Holm correction revealed significant differences between pairs 2-3 ($p \leq 0.05$) and 3-4 ($p \leq 0.03$).

Under broadband illumination, reconstruction accuracy degraded, with RMSE increasing to approximately $0.6 \mu\text{rad}$, corresponding to about 15% of the maximum tilt amplitude. Statistically significant differences between sub-apertures were observed for both tilt axes (Friedman test, $p \leq 0.01$), indicating spatially non-uniform performance. For Y-axis tilts, post-hoc Wilcoxon tests with Holm correction revealed significant differences ($p \leq 0.03$) for all mirror pairs except 3-4. For X-axis tilts, significant differences ($p \leq 0.03$) were observed for all mirror pairs. This overall degradation is consistent with chromatic averaging of the PSF, which reduces the contrast of interference features used for tilt estimation.

MAE and R^2 values reported in Tables 1 and 2 exhibited trends consistent with the RMSE results.

For piston differences between mirror pairs, the Friedman test indicated significant differences ($p \leq 0.01$). Post-hoc pairwise Wilcoxon tests with Holm correction revealed significant differences ($p \leq 0.01$) for most mirror pairs. Exceptions were observed for the following combinations: 1-2 with 1-4 and 3-4, 1-3 with 2-4, and 1-4

Figure 2. Predicted versus true tilt values along the Y (blue) and X (orange) axes across mirror pairs within a range of $\pm 4 \mu\text{rad}$. The upper panel corresponds to monochromatic illumination, while the lower panel corresponds to broadband illumination. The dashed black line ($y = x$) indicates perfect agreement between predicted and true values.

with 3-4. These results suggest that piston reconstruction performance varies across mirror pairs, with some combinations exhibiting systematically larger deviations.

Overall, under broadband illumination the model remains sensitive to tilts along both axes and relative piston differences, although reconstruction accuracy varies across sub-apertures. This behavior is likely influenced by the spatial configuration of the primary mirrors and the information content available in the PSFs.

3.2 Zemax Telescope Model

The performance of the regression model for estimating tilts along the X and Y axes, as well as piston for M1, is summarized in Table 4 for the generated Zemax datasets. Scatter plots of the predicted versus true tilt values,

Figure 3. Predicted versus true piston differences across mirror pairs within a range of $\pm 10 \mu\text{m}$ for broadband illumination. The dashed black line ($y = x$) indicates perfect agreement between predicted and true values.

together with piston predictions when applicable, are shown in Figures 4, 5, and 6.

Table 4. Performance of the regression models for Zemax datasets in estimating tilts along the X and Y axes, and piston for M1. Metrics include RMSE, MAE, and R^2 , reported as the mean and standard deviation from 10-fold cross-validation.

Dataset	DOF	RMSE (μrad)	MAE (μrad)	R^2
M1 (pair 1) independently varied	Tilt Y	0.1395 ± 0.0385	0.0975 ± 0.0244	0.9989 ± 0.0006
	Tilt X	0.1383 ± 0.0153	0.1026 ± 0.0138	0.9989 ± 0.0003
M1 (pair 1) simultaneously varied	Tilt Y	1.6692 ± 0.8753	0.9635 ± 0.4552	0.8939 ± 0.0871
	Tilt X	2.9378 ± 1.4225	2.3219 ± 1.2066	0.6667 ± 0.2698
M1 (pairs 1 & 2) simultaneously varied	Tilt Y (pair 1)	2.6092 ± 0.1808	1.9683 ± 0.1519	0.7771 ± 0.0305
	Tilt X (pair 1)	3.9629 ± 0.2347	3.1777 ± 0.1915	0.5116 ± 0.0598
	Tilt Y (pair 2)	2.4170 ± 0.1369	1.7739 ± 0.0893	0.8241 ± 0.0196
	Tilt X (pair 2)	4.1242 ± 0.1249	3.3595 ± 0.0963	0.5028 ± 0.0303
Dataset	DOF	RMSE (μm)	MAE (μm)	R^2
M1 (pair 1) simultaneously varied	Piston	0.1815 ± 7.9419	0.1450 ± 6.9147	0.5505 ± 0.3358

Figure 4. Predicted versus true tilt values for M1 (pair 1) from the independently varied dataset. Y-axis tilts are shown in blue, X-axis tilts in orange. The dashed black line ($y = x$) indicates perfect agreement between predicted and true values.

Figure 5. Predicted versus true tilt values along the Y (blue) and X (orange) axes, and piston values (pink) for M1 (pair 1) from the simultaneously varied dataset. The dashed black line ($y = x$) indicates perfect agreement between predicted and true values.

Figure 6. Predicted versus true tilt values along the Y (blue) and X (orange) axes for M1 (pairs 1 and 2) from the simultaneously varied dataset. The dashed black line ($y = x$) indicates perfect agreement between predicted and true values.

For the dataset in which M1 was independently varied, tilts along both axes were reconstructed with high accuracy. The RMSE reached approximately $0.14 \mu\text{rad}$ over a $\pm 10 \mu\text{rad}$ dynamic range, corresponding to about 1% of the maximum tilt amplitude, with R^2 values close to 0.999 for both axes. The concentration of points near zero in Figure 4 arose from the dataset combination, when tilts along one axis were loaded, the tilts along the other axis were set to zero.

Additionally, a classification model was trained on this dataset to identify, using labels, the type of perturbation applied to the primary mirror (tilt along the X or Y axis). The binary classifier consisted of two 2D convolutional layers with ReLU activation and max pooling, followed by three fully connected layers with ReLU activation,

except for the final output layer. The classifier achieved near-perfect performance, with precision, recall, and F1-scores above 99% for both tilt axes.

When all DOF were simultaneously varied for the primary mirror (pair 1), tilts along X and Y axes together with piston, reconstruction accuracy decreased. Tilt reconstruction along the Y axis achieved an RMSE of approximately $1.7 \mu\text{rad}$, corresponding to about 17% of the maximum amplitude, while the RMSE for X-axis tilts increased to nearly $3 \mu\text{rad}$ ($\approx 30\%$ of the maximum amplitude). The corresponding R^2 values also decreased, particularly for the X axis, indicating that tilt estimation becomes more challenging when multiple perturbations are present simultaneously.

In a more complex scenario, where two primary mirrors (pairs 1 and 2) were simultaneously perturbed, reconstruction accuracy decreased further. RMSE values ranged between approximately 2.4 and $4.1 \mu\text{rad}$ depending on the mirror and axis. This degradation was expected given the increased dimensionality of the regression problem and the limited dataset size. Consistent with the previously observed trend, tilts along the Y axis were reconstructed more reliably than those along the X axis. This behavior may reflect a reduced sensitivity of the focal-plane intensity distribution to X-axis tilts in the Zemax configuration.

Piston reconstruction for M1 (pair 1) exhibited moderate performance, with relatively large variability across cross-validation folds ($R^2 \approx 0.55$). Note that piston can be retrieved in our simulations due to its definition in the Zemax model. In this context, piston is defined as a displacement along the local surface normal (z-axis) in a mirror-centered coordinate system. As such, it does not correspond to a true global piston mode but rather to a local mechanical degree of freedom, which introduces measurable intensity variations in the focal plane.

Model performance was influenced by both the number of DOF and the dataset size. Consequently, the scatter plots were sparser than those obtained for HCIPy datasets, reflecting the substantially longer computation time required to generate Zemax datasets (hours compared to days).

Notably, the CNN architecture was originally developed for the HCIPy telescope model with monochromatic illumination and was not modified for the subsequent HCIPy or Zemax datasets, demonstrating its generalization capability across independent telescope models.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The implemented CNN-based control strategy demonstrates the feasibility of autonomous, data-driven control systems for future large-scale interferometric telescopes. Specifically, this framework enables the validation and optimization of alignment strategies within SELF, both in simplified optical simulations and in more detailed optical models, facilitating the transition from incoherence to full coherence in the system.

Overall, the regression model performs well on both HCIPy and Zemax datasets. However, these two modeling approaches are based on different parameterizations of the optical system, which prevents a direct comparison. For HCIPy, tilt reconstruction under monochromatic illumination achieves spatially uniform accuracy along the Y axis, with small variations along the X axis. Under broadband illumination, errors increase due to chromatic averaging effects. Piston differences between mirror pairs are reliably recovered in the broadband case, although some mirror-dependent variability remains. For the Zemax simulations, tilt reconstruction exhibits consistent behavior across datasets, while piston estimation for M1 (pair 1) is also achievable due to its definition as a local mechanical displacement within the model.

These results demonstrate that the CNN generalizes effectively across independent telescope models by exploiting subtle residual features in the interference patterns. Both tilts and piston can be estimated with good accuracy under different illumination conditions and dataset configurations. Analysis of system sensitivity across varying perturbation levels highlights the robustness of the method even under degraded conditions. HCIPy enables faster generation of large datasets, resulting in more uniform tilt reconstruction, whereas the Zemax provides a more detailed optical representation of the system at the expense of significantly longer computation times.

Future work will focus on extending the models and improving realism. For HCIPy, this includes enhancing the CNN architecture as well as incorporating atmospheric turbulence and realistic noise into simulated images. For Zemax, the analysis will be expanded to include perturbations of additional sub-apertures, both primary and secondary mirrors, together with a tailored CNN architecture capable of accommodating a larger number of DOF. Finally, laboratory experiments will be conducted to validate these approaches under real-world conditions, closing the loop between simulation and experimental implementation.

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References

- [1] Jeff Kuhn et al. "Creating ground-based telescopes for imaging interferometry: SELF and ELF". In: *Light: Advanced Manufacturing* 6.3 (2025), pp. 459–473.
- [2] Jeff Kuhn et al. "The small-ELF project: toward an ultra-large coronagraphic optical receiver". In: *Ground-Based and Airborne Telescopes IX*. Vol. 12182. SPIE. 2022, pp. 161–184.
- [3] Auxiliadora Padrón-Brito, Natalia Marrero, and Jeff Kuhn. "Co-phasing the distributed aperture of a Fizeau interferometer via photonic lanterns and machine learning". In: *Ground-based and Airborne Telescopes X*. Vol. 13094. SPIE. 2024, pp. 983–993.
- [4] Auxiliadora Padrón-Brito et al. "Focal-plane wavefront sensing with moderately broadband light using a short multi-mode fiber". In: *arXiv preprint arXiv:2510.03058* (2025).
- [5] Auxiliadora Padrón-Brito et al. "Focal-plane wavefront sensing with narrowband light using a short multi-mode fiber". In: *Opt. Express* 34.6 (Mar. 2026), pp. 9612–9625. DOI: [10.1364/OE.580986](https://doi.org/10.1364/OE.580986). URL: <https://opg.optica.org/oe/abstract.cfm?URI=oe-34-6-9612>.
- [6] E. H. Por et al. "High Contrast Imaging for Python (HCIPy): an open-source adaptive optics and coronagraph simulator". In: *Adaptive Optics Systems VI*. Vol. 10703. Proc. SPIE. 2018. DOI: [10.1117/12.2314407](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2314407). URL: <https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2314407>.
- [7] Ansys, Inc. *Ansys Zemax OpticStudio*. Version 2024 R2.01. 2024. URL: <https://www.ansys.com/products/optics/ansys-zemax-opticstudio>.
- [8] Diederik P Kingma and Jimmy Ba. "Adam: A method for stochastic optimization". In: *arXiv preprint arXiv:1412.6980* (2014).